

Conference: Online, 15-18 March 2021
Conference Director: Tristan Loraine
Publisher: London, UK: GCAQE (<https://gcaqe.org>)
Editors: Dieter Scholz, Susan Michaelis

Aerotoxic Syndrome, the Heart and Organophosphates

BURDON, Jonathan ^{1*}, HOWARD, C. Vyvyan ², MICHAELIS, Susan ³

¹ Respiratory Physician, East Melbourne, Australia

² Centre for Molecular Biosciences, University of Ulster, UK

³ Occupational and Environmental Health Research Group, University of Stirling/ Michaelis Aviation Consulting, West Sussex, England

E-Mail: jburdon@bigpond.net.au

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this presentation is to increase the awareness of the cardiac effects of OP toxicity in aircrew exposed to FEs. Two case vignettes of aircrew experiencing OP toxicity as a result of FE exposures are presented as an introduction to the subject of the present paper.

Keywords

aerotoxic syndrome, cardiac disease, organophosphates

1 Introduction

Aerotoxic Syndrome was first described by Winder and Balouet ¹ in 2000 to describe a collection of predominantly neurologic and respiratory symptoms experienced by aircrew following exposure to pyrolysed jet engine oil leaking into the bleed air and thus contaminating the aircraft cabin air (fume events – FEs). These fumes contain a cocktail of volatile organic hydrocarbons many of which are known to be toxic including organophosphates (OPs). The latter are included in jet engine lubricating oils as an anti-wear additive. Since the original description, medical complaints affecting all organ systems have been recorded following a FE ². The effects of exposure may be transient, prolonged and sometime permanent. The term and existence of ‘Aerotoxic Syndrome’ is criticized by some groups but the authors have used in the present context as it is the term used in the original publication ¹.

2 Case presentations

Case 1: A 34 year old male pilot who had been exposed to three FEs over a three month period about two years prior to presentation was seen complaining of symptoms of nausea, light-headedness, foggy thinking, cognitive dysfunction, fatigue tremor, grey skin, eye irritation, cough, breathlessness and palpitations. The latter increased with exercise. A detailed cardiac assessment showed a rapid irregular heart rate at rest with frequent ventricular ectopic beats.

How to cite this paper: BURDON, Jonathan, HOWARD, C. Vyvyan, MICHAELIS, Susan, 2021. Aerotoxic Syndrome, the Heart and Organophosphates. *Aircraft Cabin Air International Conference 2021 (Online, 15-18 March 2021)*. London, UK: GCAQE. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6383345>

Author contributions: Jonathan Burdon wrote the paper and all authors contributed to the content.

Review process: Editorial review. The corresponding author is marked with *.

Related presentation: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730409>

Case 2: A 41 year old female flight attendant presented following a significant FE event complaining of mild headache, nausea, dizziness, cough, breathlessness and palpitations. She was also suffering from balance and gait difficulties, poor short-term memory and cognitive impairment. Her dizziness, particularly on standing up, and palpitations continued and when examined four years later a diagnosis of Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome (POTS) was made.

3 Organophosphate poisoning – general comments

Organophosphate toxicity is well known in the general community and is usually the result of poisoning following their use in agriculture (pesticides and herbicides) but accidental and suicidal poisonings are not uncommon. Inhalation is the usual portal of entry but OPs may also be absorbed through the skin, conjunctivae or ingested. With these exposures cardiac toxicity is common and usually manifested by ECG changes, myocardial damage with impaired cardiac function, abnormal cardiac rhythms some of which are serious enough to cause death. Other toxic effects of OPs include cough, breathlessness, chest pain/tightness, salivation, tearing, sweating, nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, headache, visual disturbance, confusion and cognitive impairment, tremor, dizziness, loss of balance and sometimes coma. Most poisonings in the agricultural and community follow large and usually accidental exposures and serious cardiac abnormalities are frequent^{3,4}. Death from accidental and suicidal intent are well recognised⁴.

Toxicity is largely related to myocardial irritability manifested by cardiac rhythm disturbances, such as slow, rapid (palpitations) or irregular heart rates. Electrical abnormalities of the heartbeat are also common, for example ST-T wave changes and Prolonged Q-T Syndrome, the latter which may prompt life threatening arrhythmias, such as atrial fibrillation, ventricular tachycardia or fibrillation and Torsades de Pointe with the latter two causing death if not promptly treated.

4 Aerotoxic Syndrome, the heart and organophosphates

OP cardiac toxicity has long been recognised in the non-aircraft setting but in the fume event setting it attracts less consideration and is infrequently recognised by the medical profession. The reason for this is probably due to OP concentrations being significantly smaller in cabin air after a FE in comparison to that found in agricultural and industrial settings. FE may also affect passengers and very low exposures to the OP tri-o-cresyl phosphate have been reported⁵. As a result of the smaller cabin air OP concentrations, cardiac abnormalities are much less frequent. While there are no systematically documented reviews into the alterations in heart rate and/or blood pressure after FEs, cardiac abnormalities reported by aircrew after FEs have been documented².

Higher rates of heart disease have been reported by flight attendants exposed to cabin air contaminants in one study suggesting that they may be related⁶. However, this association was not confirmed in a later study⁷.

In the community setting and at the pathological level, patchy myocardial and pericardial damage has been reported in acute OP poisoning as a result of direct cardiac toxicity and may be a factor in serious cardiac complications. The authors warn that these findings may not result in ECG or echocardiographic changes and, for this reason, cardiac monitoring is warranted⁸.

An aircrew postmortem study identified lymphocytic myocarditis, which was thought to be related to OPs⁹. A UK coroner referring to other aircrew postmortem cases noted that, in two cases of young fit aircrew, there was evidence of lymphocytic myocarditis and peripheral nerve damage⁹. In another report, a left ventricular myocardial biopsy showed the histological features of a toxic myocarditis¹⁰. For obvious reasons, as cardiac diagnostic procedures, e.g.

ECG, echocardiogram recordings, stress tests and myocardial perfusion scans, are not routinely undertaken prior to or in-flight, the pre-mortem cardiac status of affected persons has not been described.

Thus, it is clear that OP exposure may lead to cardiotoxicity following a FE and has been shown to cause rhythm disturbances and myocardial damage. As the latter may be present in the absence of clinical signs and ECG changes, it is important to consider more detailed cardiac investigations in all cases, particularly if cardiotoxicity is suspected.

5 Summary

In summary, OP induced cardiac toxicity is common in the general agricultural community where significant exposures occur as a result of the use of herbicides and pesticides. Present knowledge suggests it is less frequent in association with aircraft cabin FEs but the current literature is limited on the subject and there have been no systematic studies conducted. Experience and the limited literature suggests that FEs may cause cardiac abnormalities and that these may be transient or long standing. More studies are needed.

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